

**RANKING INFLUENTIAL FACTORS ON SERVICE QUALITY
IN THE SERVQUAL MODEL USING THE AHP
METHOD (A CASE STUDY OF FINANCIAL
ORGANIZATIONS IN HERAT AND
BADGHIS PROVINCES, AFGHANISTAN)**

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Abstract

This study focuses on identifying and ranking the factors influencing the quality of services provided by financial organizations in Herat and Badghis provinces, Afghanistan. This study is descriptive in terms of research method and practical in terms of its purpose. The sampling method used in this study is non-random and purposeful. Initially, an open-ended questionnaire was distributed to 16 finance and banking experts to identify the factors influencing service quality. The final questionnaire was developed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method, with pairwise comparisons based on the SERVQUAL model. The pairwise comparisons questionnaire was conducted by a total of 26 participants. According to the results, all the matrices formed for the pairwise comparisons are completely consistent (CR<0.1). The research results have shown that the influential factors on the quality of services provided by financial organizations in Herat and Badghis provinces of Afghanistan are ranked as follows: Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, and Tangibility in the last rank. Financial organizations in Afghanistan are ranked as follows: Government banks with a weight of 0.585 in the first rank, Private banks with a weight of 0.254 in the second rank, and Exchange offices with a weight of 0.160 in the last rank.

Key words: AHP, SERVQUAL, Quality

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SERVQUAL MODELİNDE HİZMET KALİTESİNE ETKİ EDEN FAKTÖRLERİN AHP YÖNTEMİ KULLANILARAK SIRALANMASI (AFGANİSTAN'IN HERAT VE BADGHIS ŞEHİRLERİNDEKİ FİNANSAL KURULUŞLARINA YÖNELİK BİR VAKA ÇALIŞMASI)

Özet

Bu çalışma, Afganistan'ın Herat ve Badghis şehirlerinde faaliyet gösteren finans kuruluşları tarafından sunulan hizmetlerin kalitesini etkileyen faktörleri belirleme ve sıralamaya odaklanmaktadır. Bu çalışmada kullanılan örnekleme yöntemi rastgele olmayan ve amaçlıdır. İlk olarak, hizmet kalitesini etkileyen faktörleri belirlemek için başlangıçta 16 finans ve bankacılık uzmanına açık uçlu bir anket dağıtılmıştır. Son anket, SERVQUAL modelindeki çiftli karşılaştırmaları kullanarak Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci (AHP) yöntemini kullanarak geliştirilmiştir. Çiftli karşılaştırmalar anketi, toplam 26 katılımcı tarafından yapılmıştır. Çiftli karşılaştırmaların sonuçlarına göre, tüm matrisler tamamen tutarlıdır (CR<0.1). Araştırma sonuçları, Afganistan'ın Herat ve Badghis şehirlerindeki finans kuruluşları tarafından sunulan hizmetlerin kalitesini etkileyen etkili faktörler aşağıdaki gibi sıralandığını gösterilmektedir: Güvence birinci sıradadır, güvenilirlik ikinci sıradadır, tepki verme üçüncü sıradadır, empati dördüncü sıradadır ve somutluk en son sıradadır. Afganistan'daki finansal kuruluşlar aşağıdaki sıralamaya göre sıralanmıştır: Birinci sırada 0.585 ağırlıkla Hükümet bankaları, ikinci sırada 0.254 ağırlıkla Özel bankalar ve son sırada 0.160 ağırlıkla Döviz büroları yer almaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: AHP, SERVQUAL, Kalite

INTRODUCTION

One of the important goals of service institutions, such as financial organizations, is to meet the needs of their customers. Customer-centricity is considered a key factor in the success of organizations (Brady, 2001). Because financial service organizations operate in an environment with undifferentiated products, service quality is recognized as a powerful competitive tool. The importance of service quality is significant due to its substantial impact on cost reduction, increased customer satisfaction, customer retention, profitability, and word-of-mouth advertising (Buttle, 1996). In today's world, financial service organizations are forced to provide more diversified and higher-quality services to ensure survival and profitability in the face of increasing competition. The provision of high-quality services can be used as a tool to achieve sustainable competitive advantage by closing the gap between the service customers perceive and what they anticipate. The Service quality is determined by the differential between customers' pre-service expectations and their post-service perceptions of the received services from an organization. (George et al., 2013). The American Society for Quality defines quality as follows: Quality is said to be a specific set of characteristics and features of a product and services that can meet the apparent and hidden needs of the buyer. It is evident that this

definition revolves around customer-centricity and indicates that if a company can provide goods and services that meet the needs, desires, and expectations of customers, it is considered to have the necessary quality. A company that can meet most of the customer's needs most of the time will have higher quality (Crosby, 1984).

Various methods have been proposed for measuring service quality in marketing, with the SERVQUAL scale being one of the most famous. The SERVQUAL model was developed by Parasuraman and Zeithaml (Caruana and Ewing, 2000). The SERVQUAL model is among the models designed to assess service quality by examining the disparity between customer expectations and their actual perceptions. This model is also referred to as the Gap Analysis Model (Brooks et al., 1999).

All measurement tools for service quality provided by financial organizations include various factors, and not all of these factors have an equal and uniform impact on customer satisfaction with the received service. Understanding which factors can exert the most substantial influence on customer satisfaction holds paramount significance for organizations. Sub-organizations, by ranking the factors affecting the quality of services provided, can better plan to attract and retain customers and be more successful in cost management.

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Various scientific approaches exist for ranking factors, and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) stands out as one of the most frequently employed approaches in this regard. This study involves developing a prioritization of the significant factors impacting the service quality of financial organizations in Afghanistan, employing the SERVQUAL model and implementing the AHP approach. Data were collected through a questionnaire that contained pairwise comparisons of criteria (factors influencing the quality of services provided by financial organizations) and pairwise comparisons of alternatives (financial organizations) based on each criterion. The pairwise comparisons questionnaire was completed by 26 respondents, criteria and options were ranked based on the AHP method. To date, no research in Afghanistan has used this approach to assess the quality of services provided by financial organizations based on the SERVQUAL model using a multi-criteria decision-making method, making this research the first of its kind in this field.

Financial organizations in Afghanistan include government banks, private banks, and exchange offices, which were used as alternatives in this research. This research considers

tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy as the key criteria for evaluating the factors that impact the quality of services offered by financial organizations, as per the SERVQUAL model. To date, no research in Afghanistan has been conducted using this approach, which assesses the quality of services provided by financial organizations based on the SERVQUAL model using a multi-criteria decision-making method, making this study the first of its kind in this field.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pak and colleagues (2015) conducted a study titled "A Multi-Criteria Fuzzy Decision-Making Approach for Evaluating Intangible Resources Affecting Quality." According to the results of this research, five intangible resources, including human resources, organizational resources, technological resources, relational resources, and safety resources, were identified as effective factors in producing quality services, with relational resources being the most important.

Mirfakhraldini and Amiri (2010) carried out a study titled "Providing Solutions for Enhancing Electronic Banking Services with a BSC, Fuzzy ANP, and Fuzzy TOPSIS Approach." According to the results of this research, indicators such as trust in electronic banking services, protection of customer information from hackers, and trust in the bank's name in delivering electronic banking services were of very high importance.

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Chung Hu and Che Liao (2011) evaluated the quality of online banking electronic services using fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making. Based on the results of this research, the factors affecting quality were ranked as follows: tangibility, efficiency, responsiveness, continuous improvement, system availability, reliability, reputation, and privacy preservation.

Baki and colleagues (2009) studied transportation services in Turkey using a complex model combining SERVQUAL, Kano, and GFD quality performance development. The Kano model's analysis reveals that among the 27 service quality attributes, ten fall into the "attractive" category, indicating their significant impact on consumer satisfaction. When applying the customer priority level of Quality Function Deployment (QFD), we pinpoint the top three service quality attributes that hold utmost importance: VIP Service, providing advance notice to customers regarding delivery times, and collecting deliveries directly from customers' locations. Furthermore, when considering technical

requirements, reinforcing the information technology infrastructure emerges as the most critical area to concentrate on, signifying its highest technical importance level.

Bağcı and colleagues (2017) ranked the activities of Korum banks based on AHP and TOPSIS techniques using the SERVQUAL model. According to the results of this research, trust, assurance, physical appearance, and customer empathy were among the effective factors in the quality of banking services in order of their mention.

Karimi and colleagues (2015) statistically showed that customer satisfaction was not the same for all the studied banks, and a hierarchical analytical process based on the TOPSIS technique ranks banks using five components of the SERVQUAL method, such as tangibility, reliability, assurance, responsiveness, and empathy.

Supriyanto and colleagues (2021) have studied the impact of service quality provided by banks on customer loyalty, the way customer satisfaction affects their loyalty to banks, and the combined impacts of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty were examined. Findings indicate that while service quality does not directly affect customer loyalty, it does significantly contribute to customer satisfaction, ultimately influencing customer loyalty. Furthermore, service quality indirectly influences customer loyalty by way of its impact on customer satisfaction. (Supriyanto et al., 2021).

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Fida and colleagues (2020) In a research study utilizing the SERVQUAL model, the study focused on assessing the impact of service quality on customer loyalty and satisfaction within four Islamic banks operating in Oman. The results of the research indicate a substantial correlation and meaningful relationship among the three factors: service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. Moreover, according to the regression model established in this research, it became clear that the empathy and responsiveness dimensions have a substantial and positive impact on customer satisfaction (Fida, et al., 2020).

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is descriptive in terms of methodology and applied in terms of purpose. The target population for this study consists of experts in the field of banking. The sample size including 10 financial and banking experts, 10 bank employees, and 6 active participants in the exchange field. The respondents held at least a master's degree with relevant educational backgrounds. The sampling method used in this study is purposeful and non-random.

The questionnaire used to collect data in this research was developed based on the perspective of experts in the field. An initial open-ended questionnaire was sent to 16 financial and banking experts, asking them to provide their insights on the factors influencing the quality of services provided by financial organizations in Afghanistan. After collecting the information provided by the experts in the initial questionnaires, it was determined that the common aspect of their responses regarding the factors influencing the quality of services provided by financial organizations incorporates the five factors employed in the SERVQUAL model. The final research questionnaire is based on a 9-point Likert scale, consisting of six pairwise comparison tables. The first pairwise comparison table pertains to the factors affecting quality based on the SERVQUAL model, and the remaining five tables involve pairwise comparisons for each of the financial institutions, taking into account each of the factors affecting the quality of services provided by financial institutions.

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2.1. Servqual Model

The conceptual model of services, which is now commonly known as "SERVQUAL," was designed by Parasuraman and his colleagues in 1985. The SERVQUAL model is measured using a questionnaire. The SERVQUAL questionnaire, with 22 questions, first identifies customer expectations of a service provider and then measures their satisfaction with the received services in each of the five factors mentioned above (Allan, 2004).

After extensive research, this model evolved into a widely accepted instrument for evaluating service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1985). The SERVQUAL model has gained substantial recognition as a universal framework for evaluating and quantifying service excellence. A. Parasuraman, Valarie Zeithaml, and Leonard Berry collaborated on its development in the late 1980s. The acronym SERVQUAL stands for "Service Quality," serving as a tool to aid organizations in comprehending and assessing the caliber of their

services through the lens of customer perceptions. The framework operates on the assumption that service quality can be evaluated using five essential dimensions, as shown in Table 1 (Allan, 2004).

Table 1: Servqual Model Five Key Dimensions

DIMENSIONS	DEFINITIONS
TANGIBILITY	Physical facilities, equipment, appearance of employees, etc.
RELIABILITY	The ability to provide services accurately and dependably
RESPONSIVENESS	Willingness to help and respond to customer needs
ASSURANCE	Employees' ability to instill confidence and trust
EMPATHY	Giving special attention to individual customers

(Allan, 2004)

2.2. The Theoretical Framework of AHP

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a widely-used decision-making technique that helps individuals or groups make complex decisions based on multiple criteria. Developed by Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s, AHP is especially effective when the decision involves a high level of subjectivity and there are multiple, often conflicting, criteria to consider. The AHP process typically involves the following steps:

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The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) stands out as a comprehensive decision-making system, especially effective when confronted with complex problems involving multiple criteria. AHP enables the formulation of problems in a hierarchical structure and seamlessly integrates both quantitative and qualitative criteria. The initial step entails constructing a hierarchical representation of the problem, while the subsequent step assigns nominal values to each hierarchy level and generates a matrix for pairwise comparisons to facilitate informed judgment (Taherdoost, 2017).

To arrive at a well-organized decision and establish clear priorities, you can break down the decision-making process into the following steps:

Step 1: Problem Definition and Knowledge Requirements:

Begin by clearly defining the problem or the decision you need to make. Determine the type of knowledge or information you require to address this problem effectively (Saaty, 2008).

Step 2: Decision Hierarchy Development:

Create a decision hierarchy, starting from the top with the ultimate goal of the decision. Progress downward through various levels, which may include defining broad objectives, intermediate criteria, and finally, the lowest level representing a set of available alternatives (Saaty, 2008). A simple form of the AHP model is presented in Figure 1 (Taherdoost, 2017).

Figure 1: Sample Hierarchical Tree

(Taherdoost, 2017)

Step 3: Pairwise Comparison Matrices:

Develop a series of pairwise comparison matrices to systematically evaluate and compare elements in the hierarchy. Each element in an upper level should be used to compare elements in the level immediately below concerning its significance or impact (Saaty, 2008). The dimensions used in scoring the AHP model are presented in accordance with Table 2 (Taherdoost, 2017).

Table 2: Scores For The Importance Of Variable

IMPORTANCESCALE DEFINITION OF IMPORTANCE SCALE

1	Equally Important Preferred
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2	Equally to Moderately Important Preferred
3	Moderately Important Preferred
4	Moderately to Strongly Important Preferred
5	Strongly Important Preferred
6	Strongly to Very Strongly Important Preferred
7	Very Strongly Important Preferred
8	Very Strongly to Extremely Important Preferred
9	Extremely Important Preferred

(Taherdoost, 2017)

Step 4: Priority Assignment and Weighting:

Apply the priorities derived from the pairwise comparisons to allocate weights to the components at the lower tiers. This process involves weighting each element according to its relative importance in relation to the element above it. Continue this weighting process until the final priorities of the alternatives in the lowest level are determined (Saaty, 2008).

In AHP, one of the key aspects to be examined is finding the weights for criteria and preference scores for alternatives when given the (i, j) pairwise comparison matrix A. The A matrix consists of positive and inverse values.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ 1/a_{12} & 1 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 1/a_{1n} & 1/a_{2n} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The final weights can be obtained by normalizing any column j of the A matrix. For calculating the weights of matrices and consistency ratios, the formulas provided below have been used (Aktaş, et al., 2015).

$$w_i = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}} \quad i= 1,2,3,\dots,n$$

In this study, matrix weights are computed using the Perron vector method, with the following formula (Aktaş, et al., 2015):

$$w = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A^k e}{e^T A^k e} \quad e^T = (1, \dots, 1)$$

There are primarily two approaches for finding the values of weights under uncertainty (Aktaş, et al., 2015):

a. Logarithmic least squares method

$$LLS = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \ln(a_{ij} - \ln w_i + \ln w_j)^2$$

b. Eigenvector approach

$$A_w = \gamma_{maks} w, \quad w_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} w_j}{\gamma_{maks}} \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

The final score for each alternative, for ranking them based on the criteria used, is determined using the following formula (Aktaş, et al., 2015):

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{1i} \times p_i$$

Inconsistency Index-CI (Aktaş, et al., 2015):

$$CI = \frac{\gamma_{maks} - n}{n-1}$$

$$\gamma_{maks} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} w_j / w_i)$$

consistency ratio-CR (Aktaş, et al., 2015):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

When *CR* (Consistency Ratio) is evaluated, a value of 0.1 or less is considered acceptable. If it exceeds 0.1, it is advisable for the decision maker to reevaluate their assessments to reduce inconsistency. The calculated values for the random indices are given in Table 3 (Aktaş, et al., 2015).

Table 3: Random Index

N	RI	N	RI	N	RI
1	0	5	1.12	9	1.45
2	0	6	1.24	10	1.49
3	0.58	7	1.32	11	1.51
4	0.90	8	1.41	12	1.48

(Aktaş, et al., 2015)

3. THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

The hierarchical diagram for this research is shown in Figure (2). The upper part of the diagram outlines the research objective, which is to rank the factors influencing the quality of services provided in financial institutions (a case study of financial institutions in western Afghanistan). The second level of the hierarchical diagram represents the factors influencing service quality based on the SERVQUAL model, which are considered as criteria in this study. According to the SERVQUAL model, the criteria include reliability, responsiveness, assurance, tangibility, and empathy. In the lower part of the hierarchical diagram, research options, including government banks, private banks, and currency exchanges, are indicated.

Figure 2: Hierarchical Diagram

Table 4: Pairwise Comparison Matrix

CRITERIA	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Tangibility	Empathy
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RELIABILITY	1.000	3.688	0.686	7.000	4.656
RESPONSIVENESS	0.271	1.000	0.217	4.031	1.831
ASSURANCE	1.457	4.611	1.000	8.250	5.938
TANGIBILITY	0.143	0.248	0.121	1.000	0.484
EMPATHY	0.215	0.546	0.168	2.065	1.000
TOTAL	3.086	10.093	2.193	22.346	13.909

Table (4) represents the average pairwise comparisons of 26 questionnaires conducted by experts and employees in the field of financial and banking affairs regarding the influential criteria on service quality. Based on Table (5), which displays the normalized decision matrix and the calculated weights for each criterion, the criterion of " Assurance " holds the highest weight (0.455), while the criterion of "tangibility" has the lowest weight (0.047). According to the calculations, the consistency ratio (CR) of the matrix formed by quality criteria, according to the SERVQUAL model, is fully consistent (CR=0.1<0.047)

Table 5: Normalized Decision Matrix

CRITERIA	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Tangibility	Empathy	Matrix
RELIABILITY	0.324	0.365	0.313	0.313	0.335	0.323
RESPONSIVENESS	0.088	0.099	0.099	0.180	0.132	0.102
ASSURANCE	0.472	0.457	0.456	0.369	0.427	0.455
TANGIBILITY	0.046	0.025	0.055	0.045	0.035	0.047
EMPATHY	0.070	0.054	0.077	0.092	0.072	0.073
RI = 1.120	CI = 0.031		CR = 0.028			

Tables 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 represent the average pairwise comparison matrices for the criteria. The calculated consistency rates for the criterion matrices indicates complete consistency (CR_{Empathy} = 0.1 < 0.047), (CR_{Tangibility} = 0.1 < 1.64E – 05), (CR_{Responsiveness} = 0.1 < 0.0052), (CR_{Assurance} = 0.1 < 0.0386) and (CR_{Reliability} = 0.1 < 0.0510). In the fifth column of the normalized decision matrices, the weights for each criterion have been prioritized based on their alternatives. Based on these weights,

in terms of reliability, government banks with a weight of ($w=0.648$) are ranked first, private banks with a weight of ($w=0.257$) are ranked second, and exchange offices with a weight of ($w=0.094$) are ranked third.

In Table 7, considering the reliability criterion, government banks are ranked first, private banks are ranked second, and exchange offices are ranked third. The weights for the responsiveness criterion in Table 8 show that exchange offices are in the first position, private banks are in the second position, and government banks are in the third position.

Taking into account the criterion of accessibility, as shown in Table 9, private banks are ranked first, government banks are ranked second, and exchange offices are ranked last. Based on the criterion of compatibility, as demonstrated in Table 10, exchange offices are ranked first in terms of weights, private banks are ranked second, and government banks are ranked last.

Tablo 6: Reliability

	Pairwise Comparison Matrix			Normalized Decision Matrix			
	State banks	Private banks	Currency	State banks	Private banks	Currency	W
State Banks	1.000	3.281	5.563	0.674	0.718	0.553	0.648
Private Banks	0.305	1.000	3.500	0.205	0.219	0.348	0.257
Currency Exchangers	0.180	0.286	1.000	0.121	0.063	0.099	0.094
TOTAL	1.485	4.567	10.063	RI = 0.58	CI =0.029	CR =	0.0510262

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Tablo 7: Assurance

	Pairwise Comparison Matrix			Normalized Decision Matrix			
	State banks	Private banks	Currency	State banks	Private banks	Currency	W
State Banks	1.000	4.500	6.870	0.731	0.769	0.640	0.713
Private Banks	0.222	1.000	2.870	0.162	0.171	0.267	0.200
Currency Exchangers	0.146	0.348	1.000	0.106	0.060	0.093	0.086
TOTAL	1.368	5.848	10.740	RI =0.58	CI =0.022	CR =	0.0386

Tablo 8: Responsiveness

Pairwise Comparison Matrix				Normalized Decision Matrix			
	State banks	Private banks	Currency	State banks	Private banks	Currency	W
State Banks	1.000	0.638	0.531	0.225	0.202	0.242	0.223
Private Banks	1.569	1.000	0.659	0.352	0.317	0.301	0.323
Currency Exchangers	1.885	1.517	1.000	0.423	0.481	0.457	0.454
TOTAL	4.453	3.154	2.190	RI =0.58	CI =0.003	CR =0.0052	

Table 9: Tangibility

Pairwise Comparison Matrix				Normalized Decision Matrix			
	State banks	Private banks	Currency	State banks	Private banks	Currency	W
State Banks	1.000	0.688	4.750	0.375	0.375	0.378	0.376
Private Banks	1.453	1.000	6.813	0.546	0.545	0.542	0.544
Currency Exchangers	0.211	0.147	1.000	0.079	0.080	0.080	0.080
TOTAL	2.664	1.835	12.563	RI =0.58	CI =0.000	CR =1.64E-05	

Table 10: Empathy

Pairwise Comparison Matrix				Normalized Decision Matrix			
	State banks	Private banks	Currency	State banks	Private banks	Currency	W
State Banks	1.000	0.443	0.308	0.154	0.123	0.174	0.150
Private Banks	2.260	1.000	0.465	0.347	0.278	0.262	0.296
Currency Exchangers	3.245	2.151	1.000	0.499	0.599	0.564	0.554
TOTAL	6.505	3.593	1.773	RI =0.58	CI =0.027	CR =0.047	

In Table (12), alternatives were ranked based on general criteria. This table, which is based on Table (11), was obtained by multiplying the weights of the criteria and alternatives. While the details of ranking alternatives based on each criterion have been discussed in the above tables, in general and based on the five criteria used in the study, government banks with a weight of 0.585 are ranked first, private banks with a weight of 0.254 are ranked second, and exchange offices with a weight of 0.160 are placed in the last position.

Table 11: Consolidated Decision Matrix

	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Tangibility	Empathy
W	0.323465	0.101584	0.455131	0.047271	0.072548
State Banks	0.648	0.223	0.713	0.376	0.150
Private Banks	0.257	0.323	0.200	0.544	0.296
Currency Exchangers	0.094	0.454	0.086	0.080	0.554

Tablo 12: Total Weight Matrix (Alternatives Ranking)

	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Tangibility	Empathy	Total W
State Banks	0.210	0.023	0.325	0.018	0.011	0.585
Private Banks	0.083	0.033	0.091	0.026	0.021	0.254
Currency Exchangers	0.030	0.046	0.039	0.004	0.040	0.160

CONCLUSION

Organizations that think long-term for their sustainability consider service quality as a powerful competitive weapon and a tool to ensure customer satisfaction. The influential factors on the quality of services provided by organizations are not fixed in terms of time and place. That's why researchers in the field of marketing and economics have developed numerous models to assess service quality. In the current era, due to the sensitivity of the quality issue, not only are the influential factors on quality considered in terms of geographical locations, but also ranking each influential factor in relation to others is of great importance for cost management and more precise planning.

The findings of this research indicate that the influential factors on the quality of services provided by financial organizations in Herat and Badghis provinces of Afghanistan, as perceived by financial and banking experts, are not equally important. The pairwise comparisons questionnaire was completed by 26 respondents, including 10 financial and banking experts, 10 bank employees, and 6 active participants in the exchange field. The respondents held at least a master's degree with relevant educational backgrounds. Based on paired comparisons the influential factors on service quality based on the SERVQUAL model, the assurance factor with a weight of 0.455 has been attributed the highest importance. In other words, it is considered the most significant factor affecting the

quality of services provided by financial organizations in Herat and Badghis provinces, Afghanistan. Undoubtedly, due to the rapid political changes in Afghanistan, which significantly impact financial organizations, and in many cases, these political changes have either not returned people's assets held in financial institutions or have returned them only partially.

The reliability factor, with a weight of 0.323, is perceived as the second most important and influential factor on the quality of services provided by financial institutions in Herat and Badghis provinces of Afghanistan, according to financial and banking experts. Responsiveness factor, with a weight of 0.102, ranks third, followed by empathy factor with a weight of 0.072, and tangibility factor with a weight of 0.035 in the fifth position. The calculated weights for the influential factors on the quality of services provided by financial organizations show that the assurance factor is more than four times more important than the responsibility factor, more than seven times more important than the empathy factor, and 13 times more important than the tangibility factor. Similarly, the reliability factor is almost three times more important than the responsiveness factor, more than four times more important than the empathy factor, and more than nine times more important than the tangibility factor. The responsiveness factor is more important than the empathy factor and approximately three times more important than the tangibility factor. The empathy factor is more than twice as important as the tangibility factor.

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Government banks have been given preference in terms of security and reliability over private banks and exchange offices in a specific manner. The reason for this preference lies in the legal status of these banks, and in many cases, after political changes, people regain access to their assets in these banks. Meanwhile, due to the management of exchange offices by individuals, there is no remaining address for depositors to reclaim their deposits.

Private banks are favored over government banks in terms of accessibility. Furthermore, exchange offices are considered more important in terms of cooperation and responsiveness in comparison to government and private banks. In government and private banks, depositors are obliged to spend a lot of time in long queues to retrieve their deposits, while exchange offices make depositors accessible in the shortest possible time.

The emotional interaction of exchange offices with loyal and personal depositors is also stronger.

According to the findings of this research, which is based on an analysis conducted using the AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) method based on the SERVQUAL model, the research results demonstrated that government banks ranked first in terms of the quality of services provided to customers. Private banks and exchange offices, respectively, ranked second and third in this ranking.

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